

“PHYTOCHEMICAL AND ANALYTICAL PROFILING OF SUKHA PRASAVA NABHI LEPA: INTEGRATING TRADITIONAL INSIGHTS WITH MODERN ANALYTICAL TOOLS”

Dr. Rakshitha K.^{1*}, Sathyanarayana B.², Dinesh J. Nayak³

*¹Final Year PG Scholar, Department of Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana Muniyal
Institute of Ayurveda Health Sciences Manipal-576104.

²Principal and Professor, Department of Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana Muniyal
Institute of Ayurveda Health Sciences, Manipal, Karnataka.

³PG Dean and Professor, Department of Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana Muniyal
Institute of Ayurveda Health Sciences, Manipal, Karnataka.

Article Received on 16 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 06 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 10 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17878519>

***Corresponding Author**

Dr. Rakshitha K.

Final Year PG scholar, Department of
Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana
Muniyal Institute of Ayurveda Health
Sciences Manipal-576104.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Rakshitha K.1*, Sathyanarayana B.2, Dinesh J. Nayak3. (2025). “PHYTOCHEMICAL AND ANALYTICAL PROFILING OF SUKHA PRASAVA NABHI LEPA: INTEGRATING TRADITIONAL INSIGHTS WITH MODERN ANALYTICAL TOOLS”. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(12), 1685–1697. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Sukha Prasava Nabhi Lepa, a classical formulation described in the *Stri Garbha Rogadhikara* of *Yogaratanakara*. Transforming the traditional *Lepa* into a transdermal patch allows its administration through the navel region, providing a simple, non-invasive, and patient-comfortable mode of delivery. Transdermal systems are known for their convenient application, controlled drug release, and affordability, all of which may improve patient compliance and treatment results. This study includes analytical study of *Sukhaprasava nabhi lepa* and invitro diffusion study of Topical patch. The analytical study was carried out to standardize *Sukhaprasava Nabhilepa* and its modified topical patch formulation through detailed physicochemical and instrumental evaluations. The parameters for *Sukhaprasava Nabhilepa* included Loss on Drying, Total Ash, Acid Insoluble, TLC, HPTLC etc. The topical patch was evaluated for Folding Endurance, Tensile Strength, Thickness, and Percentage Elongation at Break, Percentage Moisture Content, pH, and Percentage Moisture Uptake etc.

The analytical parameters collectively provide a comprehensive profile for both formulations, ensuring quality assurance and reproducibility while supporting their potential pharmaceutical applicability.

KEYWORDS: *Nabhi lepa*, *Sukha prasava nabhi lepa*, transdermal patch.

INTRODUCTION

Scientific validation of traditional Ayurvedic preparations is crucial to integrate classical wisdom with modern pharmaceutical standards. Analytical characterization not only ensures quality and reproducibility but also supports the therapeutic credibility of these formulations. The present study focuses on Sukhaprasava Nabhilepa,^[1] a classical Ayurvedic preparation mentioned in Yogaratnakara for facilitating smooth and painless labor. In an effort to enhance its applicability and patient compliance, the formulation was modified into a topical transdermal patch, offering a non-invasive and user-friendly mode of administration.^[2]

Comprehensive analytical and physicochemical evaluations were undertaken for both the Lepa and the topical patch.

For the Lepa, classical parameters such as Loss on Drying, Total Ash, Acid Insoluble Ash, Water Soluble Extractive, Alcohol Soluble Extractive, pH, and Particle Size (sieving method) were assessed to establish its identity, purity, and quality. Advanced chromatographic analyses, namely TLC and HPTLC, were performed to identify and confirm the chemical fingerprints of active constituents. The topical patch underwent detailed physicochemical evaluation to ensure its performance and stability. Parameters including Folding Endurance, Tensile Strength, Thickness, Percentage Elongation at Break, Percentage Moisture Content, pH, and Percentage Moisture Uptake were analyzed to evaluate its flexibility, integrity, moisture sensitivity, and compatibility with skin pH.

Such comprehensive analytical studies bridge traditional Ayurvedic pharmaceutical techniques with modern quality control methodologies. The findings contribute to the scientific standardization of *Sukhaprasava Nabhilepa* and provide a foundation for developing an effective transdermal delivery system that retains the therapeutic potential of the classical formulation while offering improved convenience and stability.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

1. Pharmaceutical analysis of *Sukhaprasava nabhilepa churna* and topical patch.

2. To analyse the permeability of topical patch through the in-vitro study.

METHODOLOGY

Raw material standardization was done according to the API guidelines and Phytochemical test was done. Purity test was evaluated for eranda taila.

Purity test for castor oil

Procedure :Take 1ml of oil sample ,add 10ml of acidified petroleum ether and mix well ,add a few drops of ammonium molybdate reagent .immediate appearance of white turbidity indicates the presence of castor oil.

SPNL (*Sukhaprasava nabhi lepa*): Classical method of preparation of Lepa mentioned by Acharya sharangadhara was followed to prepare SPNL and further evaluated through organoleptic characters.^[3]

SPNLTP (*Sukhaprasava nabhi lepa*): Multiple formulation trials were conducted using both natural and semi-synthetic polymers to select the most appropriate film-forming base for the SPNLTP.

The polymers evaluated included pectin,^[4] xanthan gum,^[5] hydroxypropyl methylcellulose^[6] (HPMC), gum acacia (gum acanthum)^[7] and sodium alginate.^[8] Each polymer was individually formulated using the solvent casting method with fixed concentrations of glycerol as the plasticizer and extract as the active herbal component.

Sodium alginate was selected as the primary polymer for the formulation of transdermal patches due to its satisfactory performance in all evaluation criteria including organoleptic character.

Preparation of SPNLTP was done by 3 batches named Batch-1, Batch-2, Batch-3, Each batch contains 3 samples named A, B, C.

Sukhaprasava nabhi lepa and *Sukhaprasava nabhi lepa* topical patch was analysed for following criteria.

<i>Sukhaprasava nabhi lepa</i> ^[9]	<i>Sukhaprasava nabhilepa</i> topical patch ^[10]
Loss on drying	Folding endurance
Total ash	Tensile strength
Acid insoluble ash	Thickness

Water soluble extractive	Percentage Elongation Break test
Alcohol soluble extractive	Percentage moisture content
Ph	Ph
	Percentage moisture uptake
Particle size (sieve shekar method)	TLC
TLC	HPTLC
HPTLC	Invitro diffusion study
	FTIR

In Vitro Evaluation^[11]

Objective

To evaluate the drug release profile of the formulated transdermal patch through an artificial membrane under controlled conditions using UV spectrophotometry.

Materials Required

Transdermal patch formulation
 Artificial cellophane membrane
 Glass rods
 pH 6.8 phosphate buffer solution
 Magnetic stirrer with temperature control
 Beaker or diffusion cell
 UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

Procedure

1. Membrane Preparation

Prior to testing, the artificial membrane was pre-soaked in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer for 24 hours to hydrate and cleanse it of impurities.

2. Sample Preparation

A patch of uniform size (2 cm × 2 cm) was cut and weighed.

The patch was placed between two layers of pre-soaked cellophane membrane.

The membrane assembly was carefully tied to a glass rod to ensure the patch remains suspended during the experiment.

3. Diffusion Setup

A clean 250 mL beaker was filled with 100 mL of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer solution.

The glass rod with the membrane-patch assembly was suspended in the buffer such that the patch remained completely immersed but did not touch the bottom.

The beaker was placed on a magnetic stirrer and stirred at a constant speed 100rpm at room temperature or $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$.

4. Sampling

At specific time intervals (e.g., 0, 1, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24, and 48 hours), 2.5mL of sample was withdrawn using a micropipette.

Each time, the withdrawn volume was replaced with an equal volume of fresh buffer to maintain sink conditions.

5. Analysis

The collected samples were filtered and analysed using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer at a specific λ max (wavelength) determined from the drug's standard calibration curve.

The cumulative percentage of drug release was calculated and plotted against time.

RESULTS

a) Pippalimula

Table Showing the Analytical test results of pippalimula.

Analytical parameters	API standards	Pippalimula
Foreign matter	Not more than 2%	1.5%
Total ash	Not more than 5.5%	3.2%
Acid insoluble ash	Not more than 0.2%	0.1%

b) Vacha

Table Showing the Analytical test results of Vacha.

Analytical parameters	API standards	Vacha
Foreign matter	Not more than 1%	0.3%
Total ash	Not more than 7%	3.8%
Acid insoluble ash	Not more than 1%	0.6%
Alcohol soluble extractive	Not less than 9%	6%
Water soluble extractive	Not less than 16%	12%

Purity test for Castor oil: showed white turbidity

2) Sukhaprasava Nabhilepa

Organoleptic evaluation

Table showing the organoleptic evaluation of SPNL.^[12]

Drug	SPNL
Colour	Brown
Odour	Smell of pippali
Texture	Smooth
Consistency	Bolus

Physiochemical Evaluation

Table showing the Physiochemical evaluation of SPNL.

Parameters	Value (SI)
Loss on drying	7.91% W/W
Total ash	5.7% W/W
Acid insoluble ash	0.94% W/W
Alcohol soluble extractive	16.5% W/W
Water soluble extractive	14.3% W/W
Ph (10% aqueous extract)	6
Particle size	80mesh zize

TLC

Table Showing the Refractive index of raw drug, SPNL extract, SPNLTP under TLC.

Samples	Rf value	API
Pippalimula	0.2 ,0.1	0.13,0.25
Vachamula	0.1	0.14,0.73
SPNL extract	0.1	
SPNL patch	0.2 ,0.1	

HPTLC

Table Showing the Refractive index of raw drug, SPNL extract, SPNLTP

wavelength	Rf piperine	Rf extract	Rf SPNLTP
254	0.13	0.12	0.11
366	0.14	0.12	0.11

Table Showing the Quantification of Piperine in SPNL extract, SPNLTP.

Samples	Quantity of Piperine (mcg/ml)	
	Wavelength (nm)	
	254	366
SPNL	181.1	186.04
SPNL TP	198.7	202.1

Samples were selected sent for physio chemical evaluation of SPNLTP successful batch

	Batch 1(B)	Batch2 (B)
Thickness	2mm	2mm
Weight	1.01gm	1.08gm
Folding endurance	150-200	150-200
Percentage moisture content	25%	30%
Tensile strength	16%	12%
Percentage moisture uptake	35%	50%
Ph	5.9	6
Percentage elongation test	20%	25%

(a) Sieve shekar

(b) Invitro drug release

(c) Folding endurance

C) In vitro drug Release

Wave length	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
350nm	0.274	0.274	0.285	0.295	0.29	0.283	0.286	0.294	0.289	0.3	0.306	0.319
340nm	0.292	0.293	0.303	0.315	0.311	0.304	0.306	0.316	0.309	0.322	0.327	0.339
350nm		0.00%	4.01%	3.51%	-1.69%	-2.41%	1.06%	2.80%	-1.70%	3.81%	2.00%	4.25%
340nm		0.34%	3.41%	3.96%	-1.27%	-2.25%	0.66%	3.27%	-2.22%	4.21%	1.55%	3.67%

5) FTIR

The SPNL patch spectrum with key peaks at 2928.44, 1732.34, 1650.39, and 1559.82 demonstrated a successful molecular incorporation of the extract into the final polymeric matrix. Crucially, the 1650.39 peak is common to both the extract and the patch, confirming the retention of these core bioactive functional groups C=O of amides/alkaloids and C=C of aromatic rings throughout the manufacturing process.

The shift in the aliphatic C-H peak from the extract 2973.01 to the patch 2928.44, alongside the strong appearance of a new C=O ester peak at 1732.34 in the patch, suggests a molecular interaction between the extract's components and the patch's excipients.

This indicates that while the active ingredients are present, a critical requirement for controlled transdermal delivery. Furthermore, the presence of signatures in the patch corresponding to amides 1559.82.

Graph showing the functional group of Raw drug (1)

Graph showing the functional group of SPNL Extract (2)

Graph showing the SPNLTP functional group (3)

Tensile strength of SPNLTP

Key Word		Product Name	
Test File Name	MIAMS.xtel	Method File Name	TENSILE.xml
Report Date	18-08-2025	Test Date	18-08-2025
Test Mode	Texture	Test Type	Tensile
Speed	1mm/min	Shape	Plate
No of Batches:	1	Qty/Batch:	1

Graphs showing Tensile strength of SPNLTP Batch 1 sample.

DISCUSSION

Sukhaprasava nabhi lepa CONTAINS Pippali Mula, the root of *Piper longum*, is known for its pungent taste and hot potency. Modern studies reveal that its primary alkaloid, Piperine, plays a significant role in pain modulation. Piperine modulates inflammatory mediators such as prostaglandins and TNF- α , which contributes to its analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects.

- ▶ Similarly, Vacha (*Acorus calamus*) has been traditionally used to alleviate nerve-related pain and inflammation. Its active constituents, including α - and β -asarone, exhibit both anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, which help modulate peripheral and central pain pathways. This correlates well with its classical description as Shulahara and Shothahara, balancing Vata and Kapha doshas.

Eranda taila (*Ricinis Communis*), with its high ricinoleic acid content, acts as both a carrier and an analgesic agent. Ricinoleic acid is known to interact with EP3 prostanoid receptors, producing localized anti-inflammatory effects while enhancing the penetration of other herbal actives through the skin. Its classical properties as *Kapha-Vata Shamaka* make it a perfect medium for topical application in pain and inflammation.

In the modification of *Lepa Kalpana* into herbal transdermal patches, polymers and emulsifying agents play a crucial role in drug stabilization, controlled release, mechanical integrity, and adhesion. Both natural and synthetic polymers are employed to optimize patch performance and ensure reproducible therapeutic effects. Natural polymers like Sodium

alginate, xanthum gum and Gum Acacia and pectin were used in this study. Synthetic polymers like HPMC, PVP are also used. Some polymers are hydrophilic and some are lipophilic. selecting the proper polymer base is the crucial part .It is checked by physicochemical evaluation like texture, elongation etc.

Several *formulation* trials were conducted using varying concentrations of sodium alginate to optimize the physicochemical properties of the transdermal patch. Each formulation varied in polymer-to-solvent ratio and plasticizer content to optimize physical characteristics.

Each *formulation* was evaluated for film-forming capacity, flexibility, homogeneity, drying time, and ease of removal.

HPTLC analysis showed comparable piperine concentrations in both SPNL and SPNLTP, indicating stable retention of the active compound during formulation.

The similarity in R_f values among the standard piperine, SPNL extract, and SPNL TP confirms the presence of a common compound and validates the incorporation of piperine within the patch matrix.

A pH range of 4 to 6 is generally maintained in transdermal patches to prevent skin irritation and ensure biocompatibility. In the present study, the SPNLTP exhibited a pH within this acceptable range, indicating that the formulation can be considered skin-friendly.

The FTIR spectrum of the raw extract was rich in characteristic peaks that confirm the presence of key phytochemicals, notably strong {C-H} stretching at 2973.01 cm and 2927.00 (indicative of aliphatic chains in essential oils and fatty acids), and prominent aromatic/alkaloid signatures including the {C=C} or C=O stretch at 1650.39cm and 1608.70.

These peaks align well with reported data for Piper longum alkaloids and Acorus calamus phenylpropanoids. The SPNL patch spectrum with key peaks at 2928.44, 1732.34, 1650.39, and 1559.82 demonstrated a successful molecular incorporation of the extract into the final polymeric matrix. Crucially, the 1650.39 peak is common to both the extract and the patch, confirming the retention of these core bioactive functional groups C=O of amides/alkaloids and C=C of aromatic rings throughout the manufacturing process.

The observed change in the C-H peak position, together with the emergence of a C=O ester peak, indicates molecular interactions between extract constituents and the patch excipients.

These results confirm the preservation of active compounds, satisfying an essential condition for sustained transdermal release. In vitro diffusion drug release: The most prominent observation is the general increase in absorbance for both the 350 nm and 340 nm wavelengths from the first sample 0.274 and final sample 0.339. Because absorbance increases proportionally with concentration, the upward trend signifies progressive drug diffusion into the receptor medium.

CONCLUSION

- SPNL had finer particle size of 80 mesh size. Fineness of the particles determines how well the medicine is absorbed by the skin and also penetration in the skin. Increasing the surface area of medicines increases the bioavailability.
- This method provides a faster and affordable method for screening the formulation. It also reduces the need for animal testing. The laboratory testing allows to isolate specific variables like temperature and pH to understand their effect on drug permeation. Current study provides its effectiveness in pharmaceutical and analytical parameters. In vivo study and clinical studies are needed to establish the safety for pharmacokinetic and clinical efficacy of the product.

REFERENCES

1. Yogaratnakara. *Stirogagarbharogadhikara, Sukha Prasava Nabhi Lepa* formulation. In: Shastri LP, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Prakashan, 496.
2. Prabhakar.D, Shreekanth.J, Jayveera.K. Transdermal Drug Delivery Patches: A Review. *Journal of drug delivery & therapeutics*, 2013; 3(4): 213-221. DOI <https://doi.org/10.22270/jddt.v3i4.590>
3. Tripathi I. *Sharangadhara Samhita of Acharya Sharangadhara*. Madhyama Khanda. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharati, 2014.
4. Thakur BR, Singh RK, Handa AK. Chemistry and uses of pectin—a review. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr.*, 1997; 37.
5. Chaturvedi S, Kulshrestha S, Bhardwaj K, Jangir R. A review on properties and applications of xanthan gum. In: Vaishnav A, Choudhary DK, editors.
6. Abdel-Aal RH, Youssef MMA. Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose — a key excipient in

- pharmaceutical drug delivery systems. *Pharmaceutics*, 2022.
7. A review on tragacanth gum: A promising natural polysaccharide in drug delivery and cell therapy. *Int J Biol Macromol*, 2023; 241: 124343.
 8. Sachan NK, Pushkar S, Jha A, Bhattacharya A. Sodium alginate: The wonder polymer for controlled drug delivery. *J Pharm Res.*, 2009; 2: 1191-9.
 9. Lavekar & others, laboratory guide for the analysis of Ayurveda and Siddha formulation, central council for research in ayurveda and Siddha, department of AYUSH, ministry of health & family welfare, government of India, 2010; 83-87.
 10. Patel NA, Patel NJ, Patel RP. Design and evaluation of transdermal drug delivery system for curcumin as an anti-inflammatory agent. *Indian J Pharm Sci.*, 2009; 71(2): 195–199.
 11. Bedse, A. B., Nalawade, A. M., Kamandar, P. P., & Dhamane, S. B. (2023). Antitussive activity of alcoholic extract of {*Piper longum*} Linn. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Quality Assurance*, (3): 108–112.
 12. Lohar, Protocol For Testing Ayurvedic, Siddha & Unani Medicines, Government of India, Department of AYUSH, Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Pharmacopoeial Laboratory For Indian Medicines Ghaziabad, 124, 127.